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Additive Manufacturing with Nanoparticle Ink towards 4D Printing

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Introduction

- 3D printing includes a variety of technologies and materials

Thermoplastics

Photopolymers

Metals

Ceramic

manufactur3dmag.com
midwestproto.com

- Bonding different materials is difficult
- Creates interfaces with mismatching mechanical and thermal properties
- Detrimental to performance

Application

- 2D flexible electronics use thin metal films on polymer substrate

Normal

Cracking

Debonding

Cylindrical Rolling

- Interfacial stresses
- Susceptible to:
 - Large deformations
 - cyclic loading
 - Heat treatment

Chung (2016) *J Mater Sci*

Wagner (2013) *Thesis*

retronix.com

Proposed Solution

- A binder jetting process to fabricate nanomaterial composites

Nanoparticle inks in binder

- Switch inks during printing

Multi-material and functionally graded

Objectives

- Formulate a graphene oxide (GO) nanoparticle ink
- Print GO/PVOH composite
- Develop 2 step post-processing to enhance electrical/mechanical properties
 - Plasticizer treatment
 - Chemical reduction

Inkjet Printing

- High resolution, but unsuitable for nanoparticles

vecoprecision.com
smallprecisiontools.com

Device Development

- Robust nanoparticle printing with modifiable surface interactions (stainless steel, Teflon)

Device Implementation

- Mountable on any binder jetting printer body

Ink Formulation Strategy

- Surfactant tuning of ink properties

Stability

Surface tension

Wettability

kruss-scientific.com

Stability

- Increasing surfactant concentration increases instability
- Suitable range: (0.001-0.1 vol%)

1 vol%

0.3 vol%

0.1 vol%

0.03 vol%

0.01 vol%

0.001 vol%

Surface Tension

- Increasing surfactant concentration decreases surface tension
- Suitable range: (0.03-0.3 vol%)

Wettability

- Increasing surfactant concentration increases wettability
- Suitable range: (0.1-1 vol%)

Ideal Ink Formulation

- Projected ideal range: (0.1-0.3 vol%)
- Extended testing range: (0.03-0.3 vol%)

Printing Test

- Minimum particle velocity for jet formation is 2m/s.
- SS nozzles clogged frequently.
- PTFE nozzles did not clog
 - A D=152 μ m PTFE nozzle reached velocity >10m/s

Particle Velocity and Ink Formulation

- At low particle speed, ink droplets collide inelastically with powder

- At high particle speed, chose low surfactant concentration ink (**0.03 vol%**)
 - Low spreading
 - Good integration into powder

Printing

1.5x1.5cm square electrodes

ASTM D638 Type V specimens

- 2 step post-processing treatment
 - Plasticizer (for flexibility)
 - Glycerol
 - Reduction (for conductivity)
 - Hydroiodic acid (HI)
 - Hydrazine hydrate (HH)
 - Laser

Electrode Samples

As printed

Plasticizer

Hydroiodic acid

Laser

Hydrazine hydrate

Conductivity	–	$2.19 \pm 0.02 \times 10^{-5}$	$9.25 \pm 0.34 \times 10^{-2}$	$9.25 \pm 0.34 \times 10^{-2}$	1.48 ± 0.05
C/O ratio	–	1.94 ± 0.08	2.26 ± 0.39	2.48 ± 0.40	3.08 ± 0.47

Morphology Affects Conductivity

Plasticizer

Laser

Hydrazine hydrate

Hydroiodic acid

Tensile Samples

As printed

Plasticizer

Hydroiodic acid

Laser

Hydrazine hydrate

Flexural Properties

- HI-reduced: like low density polyethylene (LDPE) [modulus=56.5MPa; strength=22MPa]

Tensile Properties

- HI-reduced: Like silicone rubber [modulus=3.59MPa; strength=1.17MPa]
- Yield strain like nylon and other polyesters (strain=42.6%)

Stress/strain curve

Young's modulus

Maximum Elongation and Hysteresis

- HI-reduced: (strain=42.6%)

Maximum Elongation

- HI-reduced: 18.5% shift in 88 cycles

Hysteresis

Conclusions and Future Work

Conclusions:

- Printed GO/PVOH composite
- HI-reduction produced rGO/PVOH with
 - Conductivity
 - Excellent mechanical properties
- Suitable for flexible electronics applications
 - Porous/high surface area graphene electrodes in supercapacitors (EDLC)

Future Work:

- Use GO/metal/conductive polymer inks to print functionally graded composites
- Test energy storage/sensing/actuation properties of printed devices

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